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Proximate and fatty acid composition of *Heterobranchus longifilis* Valenciennes, 1840, oil extract from Oguta waterside, Oguta Lake, Imo State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The *Heterobranchus longifilis* oil extract obtained from Oguta water side in Oguta Local Government Area, Imo State, Nigeria, was analyzed for the proximate and fatty acid composition. A mature *Heterobranchus longifilis* weighing 2 kg was purchased from the Oguta water side at Oguta Local Government Area and was used for the analysis. The result of the proximate composition were as follows; Moisture 74.511 ± 0.66 , Protein 12.435 ± 0.457 , Fat 2.222 ± 0.059 , Ash 2.407 ± 0.083 , Carbohydrate 7.800 ± 0.915 and Fibre 0.624 ± 0.23 . This showed that oil from *Heterobranchus longifilis* is rich in crude protein, lipid, moisture and ash, as well; meet the requirements for human nutritional needs. Furthermore, oil in the muscle, of the fish were extracted using the Soxhlet apparatus of lipid extraction and were analyzed by gas chromatography to determine the composition of the fatty acid present. A total of nine (9) different fatty acids from the twelve(12) that were analyzed, were found to be present at varying degrees in the fish muscle and they include Docosahexanoic acid (2.410 ± 0.163), Palmitic acid (7.219 ± 0.064), Lauric acid (0.056 ± 0.008), Linolenic acid (28.721 ± 0.945), Arachidonic acid (0.079 ± 0.004), Gondioc acid (5.441 ± 0.043), Stearic acid (37.244 ± 0.622), Linoleic acid (13.111 ± 0.601) and Nervonic acid (5.989 ± 0.099). Stearic acid and Gondoic acid were the main saturated and monounsaturated fatty acids whereas the principal acids in the polyunsaturated groups, are Linoleic and Docosahexanoic acids. The study therefore revealed that *Heterobranchus longifilis* oil is a rich source of protein and lipid which polyunsaturated fatty acids mainly constitute. It

is therefore recommended that fish oil extract, especially that from *Heterobranchus longifilis*, should be incorporated into human nutrition as it is good for human nutrition as well as fish meal.

Keywords: *Heterobranchus longifilis*, Oguta water side, Soxhlet apparatus, lipid extraction, Gas chromatography, fatty acid, monounsaturated, polyunsaturated, Fish meal

1. INTRODUCTION

Fishes are generally defined as aquatic vertebrate that are typically cold blooded animals covered with scales and equipped with two paired fins and several unpaired fins [1]. They have gills which they use to obtain oxygen. Thus various kinds of fish vary greatly in shape, size and color [2]. About one billion people worldwide, rely on fish and fishery products, as it is a good source of protein and human diet [3-6]. The African catfish, *Heterobranchus longifilis*, is a genus of air breathing catfishes native to African. However, *Heterobranchus longifilis*, the only known extinct species of the genus, was discovered in the Siwalik Hills, India dating to the lower Pliocene [7].

Fish oil is currently under intensive scientific research due to its numerous health benefits. This oil is receiving a lot of attention because of its health benefits associated with the high levels of the long chain Omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acid (PUFA) especially Eicosapentanoic acid (EPA) and Docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) [8]. Many studies have shown that fish oil can lower the coronary heart disease, stroke, hypertension, cardiac arrhythmias, diabetes, rheumatoid arthritis, photoreception and reproductive system, depression and autoimmune disorders [9]. The most important health benefits of taking fish oil is that it is good for the functional development of infants nervous system as well as the retina particularly in premature infants [10]. Moreover, many studies have shown that fish oil supplementation increases the DHA content of blood components [11].

Fish oil is oil derived from the tissue of oily fish and contains the fatty acids which are precursor of certain eicosanoids that are known to reduce inflammation [12]. The Highly Unsaturated Fatty Acids (HUFAs), Eicosapentanoic Acid (EPA) and Docosahexanoic Acid (DHA) consumption is linked to the development of brain and nervous tissues in infants and visual function and reduces incidence of coronary heart disease [13, 14].

Marine and freshwater fish oil varies in contents of Arachidonic acid, EPA and DHA. The various species range from lean to fatty and their oil content in the tissues have been shown to vary from 0.7% to 15.5% [15]. They also differ in their effects on organ lipids. Studies have revealed that there is no relation between either one (1) total fish intake or two (2) estimated omega-3 fatty acid intake from all fish and serum omega-3 fatty acid concentrations. Only fatty fish intake particularly Salmonid and estimated EPA + DHA intake from fatty fish, has been observed to be significantly associated with increase in serum EPA + DHA [16]. Once fish oils are extracted, they require a purification process to achieve the quality characteristics that make it acceptable for human and animal consumption [17]. Since they contain impurities that are insoluble, phospholipids, free fatty acids, moisture, primary oxidation products, minerals, pigments, and even persistent organic pollutants. Impurities in the oil reduces its quality [18] and must be eliminated while maintaining the most desirable compounds such as omega -3 and other PUFA, so the refining process must be designed in such a way that this goal is achieved, minimizing oil loss and maximizing the availability of beneficial constituents [19-24].

2. EXPERIMENTAL (MATERIALS AND METHODS)

2. 1. Sample location

Oguta Lake is a fresh water lake. It receives perennial drainage from Rivers Njaba, Utu and Awbuna, which have their source in the Awka-Orlu Cuesta in north central. Imo State. It also receives overflow from the Niger. Lake Oguta drains into the River Orashi, a main river on the east bank floodplain of the Niger and which conveys River Niger's floodwaters directly to the Niger delta. The lake receives huge volumes of sediment from its tributaries, particularly the Njaba, a river that is actively and deeply incising into the poorly structured soils and unconsolidated sedimentary rock (Ameki Formation, Ogwashi-Asaba Formation and the Benin Formation) underlying the northern section of Imo State. Oguta Lake has a maximum depth of 8.0 m and a mean depth of 5.5 m, with a water surface area that varies from 180 ha in the dry season to 300 ha at the peak of the rainy season. Water level varies over a range of 2.7 m between these two seasons. The lake contains 258 species of phytoplankton in 107 genera. Despite this diversity of phytoplankton, the estimated level of primary productivity is low, an apparent reason for the low level of fish production estimated at 12.5 tonnes/annum. The lake is of immense importance to the people of Oguta. It is the source of municipal and domestic water, while some community members worship a deity associated with it. Further, it sustains tourism and a fishery, while it is also the outlet for urban sewage. The lake is recurrently dredged for construction sand.

Figure 1. Map of Oguta Lake.

2. 2. Sample Collection

A *Heterobranchus longifilis* of 2 kg weight was purchased from Oguta water side at Oguta L.G.A Imo State and was taken to the Fisheries Technology Department, Federal Polytechnic Nekede Owerri, Imo State Nigeria for proper identification. Thereafter, it was taken to Springboard Research laboratories in an ice cubed box for analysis. The fish was degutted after the dissection prior to the extraction process.

Figure 2. *Hetrobranchus longifilis* Valenciennes, 1840.

2. 3. Extraction of Oil

The extraction of the fish oil was carried out by rendering method of Sathirel et al., (2008). Soxhlet apparatus was used to separate the solvent and the crude oil, 10 ml of the oil, was extracted.

2. 4. Proximate Composition

The methods for proximate analysis were standard procedure of AOAC (1994). Crude protein content was calculated by converting the nitrogen content, determined by Kiedahl's

method ($6.25 \times N$). The lipid content was determined by high and dyer method, as described, by AOAC (2005).

2. 5. Fatty Acid Composition

The 10 ml of the fish oil was esterified, using N-hexane and sodium sulphate as a catalyst. The fatty acid was analyzed by gas chromatography.

2. 6. Statistical Analysis

Data was subjected to one way analysis of variance (ANOVA). Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) was used to identify significant differences at $P < 0.05$.

3. RESULTS. AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 above shows the result of the proximate composition of *Heterobranchus longifilis* oil which show Ash (2.407 ± 0.083), Moisture (74.511 ± 0.466), Fat (2.222 ± 0.059), Fibre (0.624 ± 0.023), protein (12.435 ± 0.457) and carbohydrate (7.800 ± 0.915).

Table 1. Proximate composition of *Heterobranchus longifilis*.

Components	Fish Oil (%)
Ash	2.407 ± 0.083
Moisture	74.511 ± 0.66
Fat	2.222 ± 0.059
Fibre	0.624 ± 0.23
protein	12.435 ± 0.457
Carbohydrate	7.800 ± 0.915

Table 2. Fatty acid profile of *Heterobranchus longifilis* oil.

Components	Fish Oil (%)
Docosahexanoic acid	2.410 ± 0.163
Palmitic acid	7.219 ± 0.064
Myristic acid	0.00 ± 0.00
Lauric acid	0.056 ± 0.008

Linolenic acid	28.721 ± 0.945
Eicosapentaenoic acid	0.00 ± 0.00
Arachidonic acid	0.79 ± 0.004
Gondoic acid	5.441 ± 0.043
Stearic acid	37.244 ± 0.622
Linoleic acid	13.111 ± 0.601
Nervonic acid	5.989 ± 0.099
Oleic acid	0.00 ± 0.00

Figure 3. Chart of the proximate composition of *Heterobranchus longifilis* oil.

Table 2 above, shows the results of the fatty acid profile of *Heterobranchus longifilis* oil. From the table above, there is the presence of nine (9) fatty acids and three (3) that are not present, Stearic acid 37.244 ± 0.622 , Linolenic acid 28.721 ± 0.945 , Linoleic acid 13.111 ± 0.601 , Gondoic acid 5.441 ± 0.043 , Nervonic acid 5.989 ± 0.099 , Docosahexanoic acid 2.410 ± 0.163 , Palmitic acid 7.219 ± 0.064 , Lauric acid 0.056 ± 0.008 and Arachidonic acid 0.079 ± 0.004 . Eicosapentaenoic acid, Oleic acid and Myristic acid, were not present.

Stearic acid and Lauric acid, were the highest and lowest fatty acid profiles respectively in *Heterobranchus longifilis*.

Figure 4. Chart of the fatty acid profile of *Heterobranchus longifilis* oil.

The results obtained from the proximate analysis of *Heterobranchus longifilis* oil are excellent indicators of fish quality. A high moisture content increases fish susceptibility to microbial spoilage and lowers its shelf life [24]. The moisture contents obtained in this study, agreed with the result of Nurnadia et al., (2011) [25], who observed 70-80% moisture in fish muscle. The percentage of water is also a good indicator of its relative content of energy, protein and lipid [26]. The high protein content of the *Heterobranchus longifillis* oil may be as a result it's carnivorous nature and known to feed on mollusks, shrimps, crabs and fish.

The protein content in fish oil, vary with species due to certain factors such as, the season of the year, effect of spawning, migration and food availability etc. [27]. Ash is a measure of the mineral content of food item. It is the inorganic residue that remains after the organic matter has been burnt off [28].

The value of ash in the study, suggest that this species of fish, are good sources of minerals such as Calcium, Potassium, Zinc, Iron and Magnesium. Carbohydrates are good sources of instant energy, which can be used in the body's development and growth [26].

Carbohydrate content of fish in this study was above known values of carbohydrates as reported in other works. It has been reported that fish lipids are mainly composed of polyunsaturated fatty acids, especially Docosahexanoic acid and Eicosapentaenoic acids, which can prevent and treat rheumatoid arthritis, coronary heart disease, diabetes and cancers. Fatty acids play a positive role in osmoregulation, nutrient assimilation and transport via the cell membrane [29].

Fatty acid profiles from the result, shows that Stearic acid was the predominant saturated fatty acid in the fish oil, this is related with the results recorded by Ackman (1989) who observed that stearic acid (C18:0) was a key metabolic in fish which level was not influenced by diet. Gondoic acid (C20:2) is the major monounsaturated fatty acid in the specie of study and it was considered to be so as a result of exogenous origins as well as reflection of fish diet [30].

The principal acids in the polyunsaturated groups were Linoleic acid (C18:2), Docosahexanoic acid (C 22:6 DHA) and Linolenic acid (C18:3). In general, the fatty acid composition of *Heterobonchus longifilis*, is similar to available data on other fish species. The fat content increased with an expelled increase in food consumption and varied among years, season and geographical area (catching grounds), in addition to individual variation in weight gain as a higher total fat content, is related to the feeding period and the size of the analyzed specie [31].

It is well documented that Docosahexanoic acid and Palmitic acid are the main fatty acids in aquatic fish [32].

Palmitic acid is needed for biosynthesis processes in fish and may play a role as a structural component of phospholipid in cell membranes [33]. It has also been suggested that fish oil is rich in polyunsaturated fatty acids and have desirable components of nutritious diet. Polyunsaturated fatty acids affect prostaglandin synthesis, hence encourage wound healing and protect against cardiovascular diseases and cancer.

These fatty acids play a vital role in nervous, vision and reproductive system development and functions. *Heterobranchus longifilis* is therefore, a rich source of protein and lipids, containing high and comparable levels of saturated and unsaturated fatty acids.

4. CONCLUSION

From the result of the present study, it has been revealed that *Heterobranchus longifilis* oil is a rich source of protein and lipids. The fatty acids profile of *Heterobranchus longifilis* oil extract, shows high levels of Stearic acid, Linolenic acid, Palmitic acid, Nervonic acid, Gondoic acid, Docosahexanoic acid, Arachidonic acid and Lauric acid, which exert positive effects on the body by providing the main nutrients and preventing diseases in the consumer.

The results obtained showed favorable dietary components and highlighted the importance of the lipid profile to the final consumer as well as the application of different technological processes to avoid rancidity.

It is recommended therefore, that oil from *Heterobranchus longifilis*, should be incorporated into daily nutrition as well as in fish meal formulation. Further studies should be conducted on the amino acid, vitamin and mineral contents of *Heterobranchus longifilis* in different seasons and catching areas as this would help in a holistic review of the contents of the oil from the named specie, *Heterobranchus longifilis*.

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